

Nano-Warriors Revolutionising Lung Cancer Treatment with Targeted Drug Delivery: A Comprehensive Review

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Received 13 August 2025, Accepted 08 September 2025, Available online 26 September 2025

ABSTRACT:

Globally, lung cancer accounts for about 12.6% of all cancer cases and 18.75% of all cancer deaths. In 2022, there were approximately 2.5 million new cases of lung cancer, thereby increasing the mortality rate worldwide. About 34 million new cases are being predicted by the end of 2050, which is about 77% increase from 2022 due to an increase in the rate of Cigarette smokers and a rise in tobacco consumption by humans. Nanoparticles are artificially developed particles with a diameter of more than 100 nm and have a larger surface-volume ratio than micro- and macro-sized particles, which permits them to facilitate interaction with different molecules, receptors and targeted cancerous cells. Nanoparticles play a crucial role in drug delivery by enhancing the stability of the drug, targeting specific cancerous cells, and controlling drug release. It has improved bioavailability and fewer side effects. Nanoparticles serve as the most suitable therapeutic agent. They are classified as Organic, Inorganic and Carbon-based. Gold, Silica, Liposomes and polymeric nanoparticles are widely used in the treatment of Lung Cancer. They confer both the *in vitro* and *in vivo* research. Use of membrane-covered nanoparticles with the membrane acquired from cancer cells is a novel approach in treating lung cancer; due to this, a biometric delivery system has been developed by researchers that can avoid the immune clearance and enhance the tumour targeting ability. The potential of nanoparticles in the treatment of lung disease is undeniable. Beyond this, the nanoparticle-based therapies have to face certain challenges and limitations, especially in tumour penetration and overcoming the biological barriers.

Keywords:

Nanoparticles, Lung Cancer, Tumour targeting, Enhanced Drug delivery, Controlled Drug release.

Introduction

Lung cancer is one of the most life-threatening diseases that develops due to DNA mutations and environmental exposures. Some gene mutations, such as KRAS, EGFR and ALK, indirectly affect the growth of cancer-causing malignant tumours by impairing the functions of tumour suppressor genes, which helps in preventing the growth of cancerous cells. According to the World Cancer Research Fund, China and the United States had the highest number of lung cancer cases, followed by Japan and India. Some Eastern European Countries,

like Hungary and Serbia, had high numbers of lung cancer mortality rates in 2022. About 34 million new cases are being predicted by the end of 2050, which is about 77% increase from 2022 due to an increase in the rate of Cigarette smokers and a rise in tobacco consumption by humans [1-3].

Lung cancers in their early stages are not too predictable, as they start with some common symptoms like shortness of breath, fatigue, and mild chest pain, but they get aggressive and most dangerous during their last stage. In the last stage of lung cancer, all the physiological functioning of the respiratory system gets

damaged, leading to Hypoxia. The cancerous cells developed drug-resistant abilities, which limit the various therapeutics from targeting the cancerous cells. They not only limit the therapeutic efficacy but also disturb the long-term effectiveness of chemotherapy [4-6].

Nanoparticles are artificial particles with a diameter of more than 100 nm (dimensions between 1 and 100 nm), and are typically chosen for therapeutic applications because of their physicochemical properties. Nanoparticles are derived from polymers, lipids and metals like gold. The applications of nanoparticles in cancer therapies were first realised by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) when a liposomal formulation of doxorubicin (Doxil) was introduced in 1995. Nanoparticles have been proven to be useful in various medicinal applications. Recent advanced studies have illustrated that nanotechnology-based drug delivery has greater potential in lung cancer diagnosis and treatment. Unlike the steroids and chemical mediators, they offer very few and reduced side effects. Nanoparticles possess an excellent ability to functionalize with ligands (i.e., small molecules, DNA or RNA strands and peptides. Based on the size, shape and material properties of the nanoparticles, they show their accuracy in lung cancer therapies and diagnosis [7-13, 25].

In earlier times, Chemotherapy and Radiotherapy were widely used in the primary treatment of Lung cancer. In Chemotherapy, they are intended to eliminate and destroy the rapidly dividing cancerous cells in the respiratory tract, but they also affect the normal cells, which may interfere with the normal physiological functioning of the respiratory organs. Some of the adverse effects of Chemotherapy include the rupturing of the hair follicles, direct toxicity in the liver and disturbance of the bodily homeostasis by organ damage. Therefore, creating new, enhanced, safer, and more targeted treatments is crucial for lung cancer. Since their introduction, nanoparticles have

changed therapeutic efficacy and targeted treatments, been closely examined in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* research, and been observed to be precise in controlled drug delivery systems [14-21].

Size of Nanoparticles

Nanoparticles are synthetic particles having nanoscale dimensions of 1-100 nm (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Illustration showing the variation in the sizes of the nanoparticles

The size of the nanoparticles divides their applications. Nanoparticles of sizes 2-100 nm are used for the diagnosis of Lung cancer, whereas the nanoparticles of sizes more than 100 nm have their applications in the treatment of lung cancer. Nanoparticles such as Inorganic, Polymeric, Metallic and quantum nanoparticles are used for the diagnosis of lung cancer and nanoparticles such as Liposomal, ISCOMs (Immune Stimulating Complexes), and Emulsion. Nanoparticles are used for Lung cancer therapies. The size of the nanoparticles plays a major role in classifying them based on their applications. The Nanoparticle technology addresses advanced research in the fields of Lung cancer therapies, diagnosis and betterment of the drugs in the future centuries. **Figure 2** below represents the classification of the nanoparticles based on their size and application in the fields of cancer treatment [7,11,12,13].

Controlled Drug Delivery Efficacy

A paradigm change in medication delivery techniques is represented by the use of nanoparticles in lung cancer treatments. Although they are effective against malignant cells, conventional chemotherapeutic drugs frequently have poor

specificity, which can result in serious off-target effects and dose-limiting toxicities that can harm organs and disrupt the normal cellular environment^[19-21].

The fundamental principle of the Nanoparticles arbitrated drug delivery is the ability to encapsulate the drug and release it at the particular site of action in response to a particular stimulus. The controlled drug delivery by the Nanoparticles includes:

- I. Drug protection – External layer stores the drug and protects it from degeneration by various actions of the biochemicals and isoenzymes secreted inside the body. Thereby, potentially enhancing the stability of the drug and its half-life [21-23].
- II. Controlled Drug Release – Nanoparticles can respond to particular (i.e., Temperature, pH, Biochemical reactions), allowing for precise controlled release of the drug [21-25,45].
- III. Enhanced Permeability and Retention – Because of compromised lymphatic drainage and leaky vasculature, nanoparticles can gather at the locations of tumour tissues. The EPR effect is the name given to the phenomenon. In this phenomenon, certain nanoparticles, especially those of sizes 10-500 nm /, accumulate in the tumour tissues. It brings accuracy in the drug delivery system [27-28].

Recent studies in nanoparticle technologies have advanced the various production of the nanocarriers, leading to lung cancer therapies. The Liposomal formulations (Lipid-based nanoparticles), Polymeric nanoparticles, Dendrimers and Inorganic nanoparticles both have different properties and specific applications [29-30].

Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles (MSNs) are more advanced developed by researchers, and pH-sensitive MSNs for the administration of Doxorubicin to the cancerous cells in the lungs are introduced. It has been observed that the nanoparticles release a minimal amount of drug in normal physiological pH, but they rapidly release the drug in acidic pH or acidic tumours. This leads to increased therapeutic efficacy and

precise drug delivery in specific amounts [26].

Targeting Specific Cancerous Cells

The nanoparticle's primary goal is to target cancerous cells in order to demonstrate its chemotherapeutic effects at specific sites while minimising side effects by avoiding damage to healthy cells. Researchers are always working to advance nanotechnology to increase the accuracy of targeted medicine delivery at tumour spots [31-34].

There are several ways to target tumour cells with nanoparticles, including active targeting, passive targeting, and targeting with polymeric, liposomal, and stimuli-sensitive nanocarriers [37].

The physiology of the tumours, which promotes the accumulation of liposomes, polymeric nanoparticles, and drug conjugates, is the primary factor influencing passive cancer targeting. Tumours with increased EPR (Enhanced Permeability Retention) effects and faulty lymphatic drainage frequently lead to growing permeability to the Nanoparticles and the Nanocarriers. Passive targeting is primarily dependent on the size of the Nanoparticles. Nanoparticles within the size ranges of 40-200 nm provide passive targeting by increased accumulation inside the tumour and lowered elimination [33,35,37].

* Matsumura and Maeda originally described the important features of tumour cells in 1896, which aided in the creation of the drug's passive targeting [36].

Active cancer targeting by the nanoparticles with the attached oriented moieties for efficient administration of the nanoparticle system to the Tumorous sites. Chains of Ligands from protein antibodies, nucleic acids, peptides, polymeric biochemicals, and carbohydrates are used by the active targeting nanoparticles. The ligands can easily attach to the receptors on their surfaces and accumulate inside the tumours via receptor-mediated endocytosis. The challenge faced by active targeting is that Nanoparticle requires proper binding capacity with the target antigen and interact with it. Active targeting is being continuously studied for improving the

encapsulation and efficacy of the drug delivery [29,37,38,40].

Nanocarriers play a major role in the specific drug delivery. The polymeric nanoparticles have significantly evolved over the years for targeted drug delivery. The advantages of polymeric nanoparticles are site-specific targeting for drug release and reduced toxicity in the cellular environment [37-40].

Liposomal Nanoparticles in lung cancer therapies

Liposomes are hollow-cored nanocarriers made of lipid layers. Only in reaction to a particular stimulus are the medications, which are enclosed at the inner edges of the nanoparticles, delivered to the intended areas. Liposomes are comprehensively studied and presented as one of the leading effective nanocarriers for targeted drug delivery, both active and passive. They have many uses in targeted medication release [29].

The unique feature of tumour targeting has demonstrated nanoparticles as drug delivery vehicles over chemotherapy. Recently, nanodrug delivery of Doxorubicin in therapies of prostate and breast cancer using silver decorated gold nanorods shows the potential and efficacy of treating cancers. Lung cancer is an increasing disease in every part of the world. Thereby, introduction of the drug via silica nanoparticles shows increased effectiveness and success rates [29,41].

The phospholipid bilayers known as liposomes are made up of a core and a shell. Liposomes are made up of spontaneous vesicles with water compartments separating them. Depending on how the bilayer assembly grows, its diameter typically falls between 20 nm and micrometres. They have a higher chance of encapsulating the medication and maintaining its stability. These materials are non-immunogenic, biocompatible and biodegradable. Polyethylene glycol (PEG) is used for the modification of liposomes, which increases their therapeutic activity. The liposomal nanoparticles encapsulate drugs for passive targeting delivery [29].

As an inhalation treatment for lung cancer,

Koshkina and her colleague employed liposomes loaded with 9-nitrocamptothecin (9 NC), which lowered lung weight and tumour foci in both lungs. Recently, PEGylated liposomal formulations have been approved for lung cancer therapies. The precise encapsulation of Doxorubicin by the nanoparticles accumulates them in the Lewis Lung Carcinoma (LLC) tumours [29].

Several nanoparticles with specific drug contents are either inhaled or introduced into the body for carrying the drugs to the tumour sites and releasing the drug for accumulation in the tumour cells or tissues. **Table 1** shows some of the drugs that are approved for lung cancer therapies and are effective [29]

Lung cancer treatments through nanoparticle-based chemotherapies against localised chemotherapies

The localised chemotherapy refers to transferring the anticancer formulations directly to the tumour sites. The power or the concentration of these drugs is so high that they not only affect the targeted tumour sites but also affect the surrounding cellular environment of the tumour tissues. This can affect the normal non-cancerous cells. In the earlier periods, chemotherapy was one of the widely used methods for administering drugs to the cancerous areas. Previously, inhaled chemotherapies have been used and accepted as a therapy for treating respiratory disorders and promise against lung cancer [43].

The delivery of the anti-cancer formulations through nanoparticles has been observed to be more efficient and safer in a variety of cancer cases. Nanoparticles can encapsulate anti-cancer formulations and maintain their stability in various pH and temperature conditions. Nanoparticles are biodegradable and biocompatible, which do not disturb the physiological functioning of the body. The administration of the nanoparticles reduces the toxicity of the chemotherapeutic agents as compared to the free localised drugs. Nanoparticles show a positive effect by enhancing the limited drug-releasing characteristics, which aids the efficacy of the breath in chemotherapy. They maintain the concentration of the drug at tumorous sites for prolonged durations. For their smaller

sizes, nanoparticles can easily penetrate and proliferate within the leaky tumorous vasculatures, which do not affect any other cells. They can increase penetration and

accumulation potential, which is more efficacious than the activity of the free drug [43-45].

Table 1. Drugs and their compositions that are introduced through nanoparticles for lung cancer therapies.

Drug	Composition
Paclitaxel (PTX)	A PTX liposome coated with hyaluronic acid (HA) that acts as an active drug targeting the mitochondria to overcome multidrug resistance.
PTX	The specific ligand peptide (T7) and the cationic cell-penetrating peptide TAT were connected with phospholipids via a polyethylene glycol (PEG) spacer to prepare dual-ligand liposomes
Afatinib (AFT)	pH-sensitive liposomes for tyrosine kinase inhibitor AFT
Docetaxel (DTX)	A15 cell surface modified DTX liposome
DTX	Hyaluronic acid (HA)-coated PLGA nano-particulate DTX
DTX	DTX-loaded folic-acid-conjugated liposomes
Erlotinib	Multifunctional liposomal complexes, where anti-epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) Apt-conjugated chitosan (Apt-Cs) was anchored into liposomes to co-administrate erlotinib and perfluorooctylbromide (PFOB) for the reversal of hypoxia-induced drug resistance
Doxorubicin (DOX)	DOX-loaded thermo-sensitive hybrid liposome formulation composed of dipalmitoyl phosphatidyl choline as the phospholipid and Poloxamer 188
Pixantrone (PIX)	Poly (sialic acid)-octa decylamine conjugate was synthesized and used to decorate the surface of pixantrone loaded liposomes

Figure. 2: An overview of the various kinds of nanoparticles (NPs) according to their size and

use.

Figure 3: Diagrammatic representation of passive targeting of the cancerous cells with nanoparticles

Figure 4. Diagrammatic representation of Active Targeting of Cancerous cells with Nanoparticles

Challenges and limitations faced by Nanoparticles in Lung Cancer therapies

The nanoparticle-oriented therapies in lung cancer face several challenges and limitations in treating lung cancer, especially as inhalation medication. The synthesising nanoparticle with fixed and specific size distribution is not always possible to pass through the various physiological conditions without reacting with the biological barriers [45-46].

The nanoparticles cannot reside at the specific tumour sides for a longer duration because the pH and temperature of the body can degrade the action of the nanoparticle [46].

The identification of the accurate physicochemical dimensions, such as the size, shape and surface chemistry of nanoparticles, cannot give a proper

conclusion of the physiological behaviour of the nanoparticle inside the body environment. The nanoparticles should resist particle-particle interaction. If these interactions occur, then they can show severe side effects. Thereby, providing a tendency to elicit various cellular immunological responses. The adsorption of protein from lipid-based nanoparticles can degrade them and disturb their physicochemical actions. Currently, there is a lack of rules and regulations needed for the manufacturing and modification of nanoparticles. Proper lab testing of the nanoparticles, which involves safety rating, encapsulation stability and functional testing, is required for increasing the efficacy of the nanoparticles. Moreover, properly reporting and evaluating the optimal designs, reproducible manufacturing capacities, pharmacological roles, toxicological profile and efficacy in clinical trials of nanoparticles are required for their modifications and data analysis [46-50].

Figure 7: Illustration showing some cellular limitations faced by nanoparticles.

Conclusion

Chemotherapy through the pulmonary route or respiratory route is observed to achieve the elevated drug amounts in the pulmonary system and decrease interactions of non-cancerous cells with the anti-cancer drug. Chemotherapies offer parenteral and oral administration of the drugs, which promise in to treatment of lung cancers. Even though it might seem like this, high levels of inhaled anticancer drugs can harm the respiratory system and damage the respiratory environment. Moreover, the delivery of

inhaled local anti-cancer drugs to the lungs does not target only cancerous cells and fails to show efficacy. Nanoparticle-based treatments and methods show great potential for delivering chemotherapy drugs directly to the lungs to fight lung cancer. Nanoparticles can encapsulate various drugs, ensure their stability and deliver them to specific tumour sites in a controlled manner. Nanoparticles can carry various substances, such as multiple anti-cancer drugs, DNA and RNA preparations and polymers.

Some of the challenges faced by the nanoparticles during drug delivery in the lungs are due to their cohesive natures and stemming from their low masses. Recent research and studies focus on advancing the deposition or accumulation of the nanoparticles in the lung tumour area, which results in high efficiency of inhaled drug delivery and minimises the side effects.

One or more anti-cancer drugs are encapsulated in these nanoparticles, but recent studies conclude that only a fraction of these drugs can be liberated from nanoparticles and show their action. Because of some limitations in analysis, it is hard to measure exactly how much drug is released, which makes it challenging to make nanoparticles that can better penetrate the body. Furthermore, if the drug is encapsulated in excess concentration, then it can affect the health of the lungs instead of targeting only the tumorous cells of the lung, which shows a degradation in the anti-cancer efficiency of the nanoparticle. Furthermore, physicians prefer systemic and parenteral administration of nanoparticles over inhaled methods due to the ease and reliability of those methods. Using nano-aggregates, big porous particles, and other methods, practitioners can deliver nanoparticles directly to the lungs. This approach works very accurately and efficiently in treating lung cancer. Using magnetic nanoparticles and targeting through ligands can help better direct drugs to tumours and make inhaled cancer treatments work more effectively. Therefore, unlike the other therapies, they do not disturb the physiological environment of the body and show their actions by maintaining homeostasis. The limitations can

be easily avoided by further studies and research, which can make them show greater potential in future.

Funding

The authors received no financial support for the research.

Declaration of competing interests

No conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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